

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center

Milestone 1 Target Enabling Package

Solute Carrier Family 7 Member 11 (SLC7A11)

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Introduction

The TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were established to provide high-quality research tools and technologies to validate and advance the next generation of drug targets for Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Data, methods, and computational and experimental tools are openly disseminated to the broader AD research community for use in drug discovery research to better understand the complex biology of AD. These resources and others are made available in a Target Enablement Package (TEP) at the Synapse AD Knowledge Portal.

Here the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center is providing a TEP focused on SLC7A11, which encodes solute carrier family 7 member 11 or SLC7A11 (light chain), also known as xCT. SLC7A11 serves as a cystine/glutamate antiporter, the functional subunit of system xc⁻ (**Figure 1**), and plays critical roles in glutamate homeostasis and the regulation of oxidative stress¹. The other subunit SLC3A2 (heavy chain) is required for membrane trafficking and surface expression of the transporter complex.

SLC7A11 mediates the specific exchange of extracellular cystine for intracellular glutamate, ensuring a continuous supply of cysteine, the rate-limiting precursor for glutathione (GSH) synthesis. As the most abundant intracellular antioxidant, GSH neutralizes reactive oxygen species (ROS), prevents lipid peroxidation, and maintains redox balance. But this can be viewed as a double-edged sword because the conversion of higher levels of cystine to cysteine requires larger amounts of NADPH, thus altering the redox homeostasis of the cell. SLC7A11 is highly regulated by oxidative stress response pathways, including the NRF2 (nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2) transcription factor, which upregulates SLC7A11 expression in response to oxidative stress². NRF2 activation enhances cystine uptake and GSH synthesis, thereby protecting neurons from ROS-induced damage. However, chronic oxidative stress impairs NRF2 function, leading to dysregulated SLC7A11 activity and increased oxidative damage.

SLC7A11 is primarily expressed in astrocytes³ where it partners with glutamate importers Excitatory Amino Acid Transporters EAAT1 and EAAT2 to regulate extracellular glutamate levels⁴. While glutamate is an important neurotransmitter, high concentrations promote synaptic dysfunction and neuroinflammation. Overactivation of glutamate receptors, particularly the NMDA class of receptors, leads to prolonged activation and ultimately excitotoxicity⁵. The levels of intracellular glutamate impact glutamate-glutamine cycling between neurons and astrocytes, influencing synaptic plasticity and neurotransmission⁶.

Figure 1. System xc⁻ cellular pathways. This antiporter imports cystine while exporting glutamate. Excess extracellular glutamate leads to NMDA related excitotoxicity. Intracellular cystine is converted to cysteine, a key component of GSH which is involved in the reduction of lipid peroxides, thus regulating ROS production and inhibiting ferroptosis. Created in BioRender.

Overexpression of SLC7A11 has been shown to promote tumor growth in part by inhibiting ferroptosis, a form of regulated cell death driven by iron-dependent lipid peroxidation⁷. Elevated expression was found in primary human glioma tumors⁸, whereas EAAT1 and EAAT2 are decreased in human glioblastoma⁹. Increased EAAT2 expression has even been shown to suppress tumor growth *in vivo*¹⁰, providing further evidence that extracellular glutamate is connected to tumor growth¹¹. SLC7A11 is negatively regulated by the tumor suppressor p53, which inhibits SLC7A11 expression under cellular stress to promote ferroptosis¹².

SLC7A11 expression is higher in Alzheimer’s patients compared to healthy controls¹³. Exposure to amyloid- β_{1-40} protein stimulates a dose-dependent release of glutamate in microglia, and injection of $A\beta_{1-40}$ into the hippocampus of adult mice resulted in increased expression of SLC7A11 transcripts¹⁴. In parallel, astrocytes and neurons treated with $A\beta_{1-42}$ showed reduced expression of EAAT1 and EAAT2 accompanied by impaired glutamate uptake¹⁵. In early AD, SLC7A11 upregulation may act as a compensatory neuroprotective mechanism against oxidative damage, but in later disease stages, chronic stress-induced p53 activation suppresses SLC7A11, leading to increased susceptibility to ferroptosis.

Taken together, these findings support the importance of maintaining glutamate homeostasis through the coordinated activity of SLC7A11, EAAT1, and EAAT2. Disrupting this balance compromises the cell’s ability to regulate redox status, sustain glutamate-glutamine cycling between astrocytes and neurons, and limits extracellular glutamate accumulation, which otherwise may lead to excitotoxicity. In this Target Enablement Package, we evaluate current tools and strategies for targeting system xc^- , particularly SLC7A11, as a novel therapeutic target for AD.

Gene Expression

SLC7A11, which encodes the light chain subunit of system xc^- , is evolutionarily conserved across vertebrates, reflecting its essential role in cellular metabolism and redox balance. While broadly expressed across tissues, species-specific regulation of SLC7A11 has been observed. Its expression in humans is enriched in the brain, whereas in mice, SLC7A11 is also highly expressed in tissues such as the testis, where it is regulated by luteinizing hormone and androgens^{16, 17}.

Figure 2. RNA expression of SLC7A11 in multiple tissues.

Analysis of tissue-specific expression data from the Human Protein Atlas (HPA) ¹⁸ and the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project ¹⁹ confirms that SLC7A11 is expressed across multiple organs, with relatively high levels observed in the human brain (**Figure 2**). Within the brain, SLC7A11 transcripts are detectable in numerous regions with low regional specificity. Notably, expression is highest in the cerebral cortex, followed by the amygdala and basal ganglia, which regulate motivation and behavior, including actions that maintain homeostatic balance (e.g., hunger, thirst, thermoregulation, circadian rhythms) via interactions with the hypothalamus. Moderate expression levels in the hippocampal formation, hypothalamus, and midbrain suggest additional roles in motor control and higher-order cognitive functions (**Figure 2**).

Figure 3. RNA expression of SLC7A11 across brain regions. ACC: Anterior Cingulate Cortex. CBE: Cerebellum. DLPFC: Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex. FP: Frontal Pole. IFG: Inferior Frontal Gyrus. PCC: Posterior Cingulate Cortex. PHG: Parahippocampal Gyrus. STG: Superior Temporal Gyrus. TCX: Temporal Cortex.

Agora is an interactive web application within the AD Knowledge Portal that integrates high-dimensional human transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic datasets to systematically evaluate gene-level associations with AD²⁰. A complementary analysis of human brain expression data using Agora further supports widespread SLC7A11 expression across multiple brain regions. All expression levels were quantified using RNA-seq counts per million (CPM), and all measured values exceeded the commonly accepted meaningful expression threshold of CPM > 5 (Log2CPM > ~2.3) (**Figure 3**).

Single-cell RNA-seq data from the HPA across diverse tissues and cell types have been analyzed to assess the cell-type-specific expression patterns of SLC7A11 (**Figure 4**). Consistent with prior findings, SLC7A11 expression is enriched in glial populations, particularly astrocytes and microglia. This pattern supports its proposed roles in maintaining redox homeostasis, modulating immune responses, and buffering extracellular glutamate in the central nervous system.

Figure 4. Single cell RNA expression level in multiple cell types for SLC7A11.

To better understand the transcriptional regulation of antioxidant pathways in human microglia within the context of AD pathology, we examined the expression of SLC7A11 in a recently published single-cell RNA-sequencing dataset that delineated 13 transcriptionally distinct microglial subtypes in both fresh and frozen tissue²¹. Analysis of this dataset revealed statistically significant differences in SLC7A11 expression levels among specific microglial subtypes, as shown in **Table 1**. SLC7A11 expression was detected across various microglial subtypes, though no subtype exhibited an exceptionally high log2 fold change compared with other subtypes. SLC7A11 expression was significantly upregulated in several microglial subtypes in fresh brain tissue. Notably, adaptive microglia, identified by the marker HSPA1A, exhibited elevated SLC7A11 expression, suggesting a potential role in stress-related adaptive responses. Similarly, proliferative microglia, marked by MKI67, showed increased expression levels, indicating a possible association between SLC7A11 and microglial proliferation. Additionally, *ex vivo* activated microglia (exAM), characterized by ERN1 expression and enriched in inflammatory pathways, demonstrated marked

Tissue	Subclass	Subtype	log2FC	AUROC	P value
Fresh	Adaptive	AIF1	-0.009	0.499	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	HSPA1A	0.009	0.501	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	IFI44L	-0.005	0.499	0.018
Fresh	Homeostatic	FRMD4A	-0.008	0.499	<0.001
Fresh	Homeostatic	PICALM	-0.009	0.499	<0.001
Fresh	Proliferative	MKI67	0.008	0.501	<0.001
Fresh	exAM	ERN1	0.022	0.502	<0.001
Frozen	ADAM	GPNMB	0.023	0.503	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	AIF1	-0.039	0.495	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	HIST	-0.034	0.496	<0.001
Frozen	Homeostatic	FRMD4A	-0.015	0.498	<0.001
Frozen	PVM	CD163	0.022	0.503	<0.001

Table 1. Differential expression analysis of SLC7A11 RNA expression for several microglial subtypes. GPNMB microglia were found to be increasingly in frozen AD patient samples statistical significantly.

upregulation, pointing to a potential link between SLC7A11 and microglial activation under inflammatory conditions. In frozen brain tissue, SLC7A11 expression was also upregulated in Alzheimer’s Disease associated microglia (ADAM), identified by the marker GPNMB, and perivascular macrophages (PVM), marked by CD163, suggesting a potential role in immune-modulatory and perivascular-associated microglial functions. Conversely, SLC7A11 expression was consistently downregulated in adaptive microglia, marked by AIF1, and homeostatic microglia, identified by FRMD4A. Additional downregulation was observed in adaptive microglia, marked by IFI44L, and homeostatic microglia, identified by PICALM, in fresh tissue, while Adaptive microglia, marked by HIST, exhibited reduced expression specifically in frozen samples.

SLC7A11 is also subject to alternative splicing, producing at least one validated isoform and one additional predicted variant (UniProt Q9UPY5). Although the functional relevance of these isoforms requires further

Figure 5. Functional interaction network analysis using IPA for SLC7A11. Red circle: Central gene, Blue triangle: Regulated by, Green square: Regulates, Yellow diamond: Binds, Solid line: Regulates, Long-dash: Regulated by, Short-dash: Binds.

validation, alternative splicing may enable tissue-specific regulation and functional diversification of the transporter.

For network analyses, we used Ingenuity Pathways Analysis (IPA[®], QIAGEN) and gathered important regulatory information on SLC7A11 (**Figure 5**). Specifically, SLC7A11 regulates important molecules, including L-cystine, L-glutamic acid, glutathione, malondialdehyde, and reactive oxygen species, highlighting its central role in redox balance and oxidative stress response. It also influences enzymes and proteins such as GPX4, crucial for preventing ferroptosis, and metabolic regulators like GPT2, PCK2, and the stem cell markers PROM1 and NES. This indicates its broad impact on metabolism, oxidative defense, and stemness.

SLC7A11 is regulated by a diverse set of transcription factors, small molecules, and environmental cues, including NFE2L2 (a key regulator of antioxidant response), TP53 (a tumor suppressor), KRAS, and environmental agents like lipopolysaccharide and hydrogen peroxide. SLC7A11 binds several proteins, including SLC3A2 (a partner in system activity), CD44 (a stem cell marker), and members of the RAS family (KRAS, NRAS, HRAS), linking it to oncogenic signaling. Other notable interactions include BECN1, suggesting a role in autophagy regulation, and immune-related molecules like KLRD1 and STING1, implicating it in immune responses.

Structural Biology, Protein Expression, and Purification

SLC7A11 is a 12-pass transmembrane protein responsible for importing L-cystine that is exchanged for intracellular L-glutamate at a 1:1 molar ratio in a Na⁺-independent manner. While L-glutamate and cystine are the major substrates of this transporter, it is known that SLC7A11 can also recognize α -aminoadipate and L-cystathionine as additional substrates²². SLC7A11 forms a heterodimer with SLC3A2 (also known as CD98hc and 4F2hc) and this complex is named system xc⁻. SLC3A2 acts as a molecular chaperone for SLC7A11 and may help with substrate specificity, but SLC7A11 performs the amino acid transport function. SLC7A11 and SLC3A2 are held together through 3 main interactions²³: a single disulfide bond that forms between C211_{SLC3A2} and C158_{SLC7A11} (**Figure 6**); an extensive interface between the single transmembrane helix (TM1) of SLC3A2 and TM4 of SLC7A11; and a hydrogen bond between the backbone carbonyl of K300_{SLC3A2} and the side chains of Q217_{SLC7A11} and Q219_{SLC7A11}. This hydrogen bond is thought to help position SLC3A2 to accommodate the larger size of cystine molecules.

The first published cryo-EM structure of system xc⁻ was released in 2020 by Oda and colleagues and solved to 6.2 Å resolution²⁴. To minimize protein aggregation and improve solubility, the Oda lab made a series of consensus-based mutations across the entirety of SLC7A11. This resulted in a SLC7A11 protein containing 101 amino acid substitutions, including mutations made in the putative substrate-binding pocket. While this approach is helpful in producing a stable complex that can be applied to cryo-EM grids, caution should be used when applying this approach to studying inhibitor-bound complexes. This mutated protein, while stabilized for structural studies, was unable to perform Na⁺-independent glutamate transport²⁴. At 6.2 Å resolution, the secondary structures of the complex can be modeled into the electron density, but individual side chains cannot be modeled with high confidence. This structure suggests SLC7A11 adopts a fold consistent with members of the amino acid-polyamine-organocation transporter (APC) superfamily. Additional information about protein flexibility can be determined from how well-resolved electron density is surrounding different transmembrane helices. For example, individual transmembrane helices

in the “hash” domain (TM3, TM4, TM8, TM9) are well-resolved while transmembrane helices in the “bundle” domain (TM1, TM2, TM6 and TM7) exhibit more blurred density²⁴. Blurred density suggests the bundle domain is flexible, which agrees with other studies that show the bundle domain acts as a gate to control access to the substrate binding pocket. While this structure helps to confirm the overall architecture of the system xc^- complex, higher resolution structures of both apo and ligand bound are needed.

Figure 6. Structural features of the system xc^- heterodimer. SLC3A2 (PDB 7P9V) is shown as gray cartoon with four n-linked glycosylation (NAG) sites shown as sticks. SLC7A11 (PDB 7P9V) is shown as a rainbow cartoon with the transmembrane helices shown below in their representative colors. The two cysteine residues that form the single disulfide bond linking SLC3A2 and SLC7A11 are labeled and shown as sticks. The insert with the blue border highlights the single hydrogen bond observed between the backbone carbonyl of K300 on SLC3A2 (gray) and the side chains of Q217 and Q219 on SLC7A11 (green). The insert with the black border shows the extensive interface formed between SLC3A2 (gray) and SLC7A11 (teal). The side chains of several key amino acids are shown as sticks and labeled. Figure generated using PyMol. Figure adapted from Parker et al.

To address this gap in knowledge, the cryo-EM structure of system xc^- was reported in both the apo (3.4 Å resolution) and glutamate-bound (3.7 Å resolution) states, along with a molecular dynamics model of cystine binding²³. Several N-acetyl glucosamine groups decorate the surface of SLC3A2 (**Figure 6**), and it was observed that SLC3A2 sits ~20° above SLC7A11. SLC3A2 placement above SLC7A11 is noticeably different from other SLC complexes, presumably to facilitate cystine binding. As was observed previously, SLC7A11 adopts the same fold as other members of the APC superfamily. In its unbound (apo) state, the transporter adopts an inward open conformation which creates an aqueous channel spanning from the cytoplasm to the central binding site (**Figure 7A**). The binding site is a patch of basic amino acids that help with the recognition of glutamate and is formed by a portion of the “bundle” domain (TM1 and TM6) and the “hash” domain (TM3, TM4, TM8, TM9). Additional important amino acids on SLC7A11 are highlighted

Figure 7. Unique structural features of apo and glutamate-bound SLC7A11. **A)** A top-down view of SLC7A11 (PDB 7P9V) cut through the center to show secondary structures (cartoon representation in gray) and the protein surface in tan. Several regions of SLC7A11 are highlighted, including the ligand binding site. Three key amino acid side chains are shown as sticks: lysine 198 (K198) in purple, tryptophan 244 (Y244) in green, and arginine 396 (R396) in orange. **B)** A top-down view of SLC7A11 bound to glutamate (PDB 7P9U). Glutamate is shown as black sticks, while the secondary structures are shown in gray and the surface representation shown in tan.

in **Figure 7A**. Glutamate is found to bind the central binding site near TM3 and TM8, which is slightly different than other SLC ligands that bind closer to TM1 and TM6 (**Figure 7B**). When glutamate is bound, there are several structural rearrangements that occur in transmembrane helix 8 (TM8). When the transporter is in its apo state, TM8 adopts an “unwound” conformation where two turns of the alpha-helix adopt a random coil. When glutamate is bound, however, the entire helix becomes ordered²³ (**Figure 8**). The “unwound” state of TM8 was not observed in the 6.2 Å structure described above, likely due to insufficient resolution. This shift from “unwound” to “helical” TM8 is also observed in MD simulations where cystine is modeled into the glutamate binding site. The authors suggest the increased plasticity of TM8 is due to a loss of a hydrogen bond with a conserved lysine (K198) on TM5 (**Figure 7**). Without a hydrogen bond holding TM8 in place, it can adopt multiple conformations.

Figure 8. Different binding poses observed on TM8. Apo SLC7A11 (PDB 7P9V) is shown as purple cartoon and glutamate-bound SLC7A11 (7P9U) is shown as salmon cartoon. Glutamate, and the side chains for V335 and F336 are shown as sticks.

A cryo-EM structure of system xc⁻ bound to Erastin has been resolved at 3.4 Å with the ligand bound to an allosteric site on SLC7A11 (**Figure 9A**), providing insight into ligand interaction with the transporter²⁵. Inhibition by Erastin has been shown to be specific to system xc⁻ as phenylalanine, arginine, leucine, and serine uptake were unaffected by cells subjected to Erastin treatment^{26, 27}. Interestingly, TM8 does not adopt a fully helical structure in this cryo-EM map, instead adopting a conformation similar to the apo structure of SLC7A11 (**Figure 9A**). Efforts to improve the properties of Erastin led to the development of Imidazole Ketone Erastin (IKE) with several functional groups added to improve solubility and metabolic stability. While no crystal or cryo-EM structures have been solved with system xc⁻ bound to IKE, MD simulations predict IKE binds to SLC7A11 at the same site as erastin²⁸. The additional functional groups added to Erastin increase the van der Waals contacts between the molecule and SLC7A11 and extend the molecule towards the substrate binding cavity (**Figure 9B**).

Figure 9. Erastin binding to SLC7A11. **A)** Surface representation of system xc⁻ with SLC3A2 shown in pink and SLC7A11 shown in teal. Erastin and 1,2-Distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphate are shown as green sticks. Inset shows a zoom in on the binding site of Erastin (teal, PDB 7EPZ) aligned with the glutamate-bound structure of SLC7A11 (olive green, PDB 7P9U). TM8 is labeled on the right-hand side of insert to demonstrate the helical nature of both structures. The glutamate ligand is shown as sticks. Figure made in PyMol. **B)** Molecular dynamics simulation of imidazole ketone Erastin (IKE) binding to SLC7A11, courtesy of M. Robo and R. Paranjape. IKE is shown as white sticks and a surface representation of SLC7A11 is shown in teal. Amino acid side chains either participating in van der Waals interactions with IKE or that help to form the proposed binding pocket are labeled and shown as teal sticks beneath the surface of SLC7A11.

While SLC7A11 is a member of the solute carrier family of transmembrane proteins, it is not anticipated that there will be major selectivity issues when drugging this transporter. Even though SLC7A9 (also known as b^{0,+}AT) can also import cystine, SLC7A11 is the only cystine/glutamate antiporter in the SLC7 family. SLC7A11 also has some unique structural features that may allow it to be drugged more specifically. In particular, SLC7A11 possesses an arginine at position 396 (R396) that is unique to SLC7A11. R396 is thought to play a major role in cystine recognition and specificity by coordinating the second cystine carboxylate and positioning the molecule within TM1 and TM6. Other SLC7 transporters have asparagine or alanine residues at this position and SLC7A11 R396N, R396A and R396K mutants have been found to be unable to transport glutamate²³. Additionally, the extracellular tunnel of SLC7A11 is not as charged as other antiporters in this family.

In all reported cryo-EM structures of system xc^- , full-length constructs of both SLC7A11 (NM_014331.4) and SLC3A2 (NM_001012662.2) are expressed. Given that SLC3A2 acts as a molecular chaperone for SLC7A11, it is not surprising that these methods require the expression of both proteins. Two isoforms of SLC3A2 are employed in the published structures that differ at the N-terminus between residues 39-98. Two groups^{23,24} used the canonical Uniprot SLC3A2 sequence (P08195), while another²⁵ opted for a slightly different sequence that corresponds to Uniprot ID P08195-5. Both constructs result in functional system xc^- . All methods that resulted in a cryo-EM structure report the addition of an N-terminal histidine tag on SLC3A2 to aid in affinity purification. These reports also used a FLAG tag on SLC7A11, and notably SLC7A11 can tolerate the addition of a FLAG tag at either the N- or C-terminus. Based on the approaches successfully used in structural studies, a recommended construct design would include full-length SLC7A11 (Uniprot Q9UPY5) with an N-terminal FLAG tag and full-length SLC3A2 (Uniprot P08195) with an N-terminal histidine tag. The co-expression of both SLC7A11 and SLC3A2 was performed in mammalian cell (HEK293F) expression systems^{23, 25}. Mammalian cell expression systems are preferred because they possess the correct cellular machinery to translocate system xc^- to the plasma membrane as well as decorate SLC3A2 with the correct glycosylation pattern.

Because SLC7A11 is a transmembrane protein, it is of the utmost importance to preserve membrane integrity when purifying system xc^- . Thus, the use of detergents is required to effectively isolate membrane fractions from the remainder of the cellular debris. Protocols report the use of several detergents, namely LMNG, CHS, DMM, GDN, and digitonin²³⁻²⁵. Detergent screening is an important aspect of membrane preparation as it can affect not only the recovery of the protein during purification but also how the protein interacts with the air-water interface on cryo-EM grids. As each research group will likely require slightly different detergent compositions, it is difficult to make recommendations on this aspect; however, the detergents listed above can serve as starting points for membrane preparations of system xc^- .

The following purification protocol is suggested based on the use of constructs recommended above. Purification of system xc^- can be effectively accomplished through affinity-based chromatography. Once the membrane fraction has been isolated, anti-FLAG affinity resin can be used to capture the FLAG tag present on SLC7A11 and effectively pull down the entire complex. The complex is then eluted off the resin through competition with free FLAG peptide. If additional purification is required, immobilized metal affinity chromatography can be employed by utilizing the histidine tag on SLC3A2. A final size-exclusion chromatography step is included to ensure the sample is homogenous in size and in a buffer compatible with downstream cryo-EM grid preparation.

Cryo-EM grid selection and preparation varied across protocols that yielded a published structure. Protein concentrations from 4.5 – 10 mg/mL were applied to holey carbon grids coated with either gold or copper²³⁻²⁵. Blotting parameters, such as detergent composition, chamber humidity and temperature, blot force and blot time, must be optimized by each researcher depending on the quality of the particles observed when screening grids on the microscope.

Available Assays

The ability to quantify SLC7A11 function is critical for evaluating its therapeutic potential in AD. Several biochemical and imaging approaches are available for assessing system xc⁻ activity. These *in vitro* assays can be categorized into the measurement of cystine uptake, extracellular glutamate, and downstream effects such as lipid peroxidation and ROS measurements (**Figure 10**).

Radiolabeled [³⁵S] cystine uptake was used for many years^{29, 30} eventually being replaced with [¹⁴C] labelling^{27, 31} for safety and increased half-life (~87 days compared to over 5,700 years). These methods provide direct quantification of SLC7A11 function and have been used successfully in many cell lines, predominantly in various cancer lines but also in microglia and other CNS relevant cell types.

Figure 10. Assay options to measure the activity of SLC7A11 including 1) cystine levels by [¹⁴C], 2) glutamate levels by colorimetric, GlutamateGlo™, and Amplex® Red, 3) lipid peroxidation, 4) ROS levels, and 5) cell viability related to ferroptosis. Image created in BioRender.

Several options exist to measure extracellular glutamate levels, such as commercially available glutamate colorimetric assay kits³². In the case of Promega's Glutamate-Glo™^{33, 34}, glutamate is converted to α-ketoglutarate by glutamate dehydrogenase in the presence of NAD⁺, generating NADH. This NADH then causes the conversion of a pro-luciferin substrate into luciferin, which then reacts with Ultra-Glo™ recombinant luciferase to generate a luminescent signal proportional to glutamate concentration. Glutamate can also be converted to α-ketoglutarate by glutamate oxidase, which also produces hydrogen peroxide. The hydrogen peroxide reacts with Amplex® Red^{27, 35}, a colorless molecule, to create the highly fluorescent molecule, resorufin. Amplex® UltraRed³¹ is the improved substrate providing greater stability and enhanced sensitivity.

There are many methods to investigate the downstream effects of SLC7A11 inhibition. Cystine import is crucial for glutathione production which can be measured by various fluorescence^{27, 28, 34} and HPLC-based^{36, 37} methods. Other valuable endpoints to monitor include ROS levels³⁸⁻⁴⁰, cell viability^{41, 42} (often driven by ferroptosis), and lipid peroxidation^{43, 44}.

Beyond *in vitro* assays, developing reliable biomarkers for SLC7A11 activity in human AD patients is essential for advancing clinical research and therapeutic strategies. Several emerging biomarkers show promise in this area. Increased cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) glutamate concentrations correlate with SLC7A11 upregulation and excitotoxicity, making it a potential biomarker for system xc⁻ activity in AD patients⁶. Measuring cystine/glutamate ratios in circulating blood may serve as a more accessible systemic biomarker⁴⁵. Oxidative stress markers such as F2-isoprostanes and malondialdehyde (MDA) can provide indirect insights into SLC7A11-related redox imbalance^{46, 47}. Emerging positron emission tomography (PET) tracers designed to visualize system xc⁻ activity *in vivo* may allow direct monitoring of SLC7A11 expression and transporter function⁴⁸. These biomarkers offer a foundation for biomarker-driven clinical trials, enabling patient stratification based on SLC7A11 activity. This approach could enhance drug development efforts by identifying AD subpopulations most likely to benefit from SLC7A11-targeted interventions.

Research on the *SLC7A11* gene has leveraged a variety of genetic and molecular tools, including knockout (KO) and knockdown (KD) studies, CRISPR-Cas9, induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), and mutational analyses, to elucidate its functions and regulatory mechanisms. KO mouse models of SLC7A11 have demonstrated its critical role in tumor progression, with deficiency significantly inhibiting melanoma development⁴⁹. KD studies in specific cancer cell lines have revealed context-dependent effects on cell proliferation and survival⁵⁰. CRISPR-Cas9 has been widely used to disrupt SLC7A11 expression in cancer cell lines, advancing our understanding of its role in ferroptosis and resistance to oxidative stress⁵¹. Although iPSC studies on SLC7A11 are limited, they offer promising opportunities for disease modeling and drug screening. Additionally, catalytically inactive Cas9 (dCas9) systems fused with epigenetic modifiers have been employed to study the epigenetic regulation of SLC7A11 without inducing DNA damage⁵². Mutational analyses targeting specific domains of the protein have begun to identify regions essential for its transporter activity and interactions, further refining our understanding of its molecular functions. These approaches collectively provide insights into SLC7A11's involvement in cancer, redox balance, and potential therapeutic applications.

While radiolabeled cystine uptake remains a powerful tool for directly measuring SLC7A11 transporter activity, its use is limited by the need for specialized equipment for the safe handling of radiolabeled materials. As a result, we suggest the use of either the Glutamate-Glo™ luminescence assay and the Amplex® Red/UltraRed fluorescence assay for routine screening and functional studies. To corroborate glutamate release data and capture the downstream biological consequences of SLC7A11 activity, a set of secondary assays is needed. These include quantification of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), assessment of lipid peroxidation, and evaluation of cell viability, particularly in the context of ferroptosis vulnerability. Together, these assays allow for the integrated assessment of both transporter function and its broader redox and metabolic impacts.

In parallel, the importance of developing translational biomarkers to bridge *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies should not be overlooked. Emerging candidates such as CSF glutamate levels, blood cystine/glutamate ratios, and oxidative stress markers (e.g., F2-isoprostanes, malondialdehyde) offer promising avenues for future clinical application. Additionally, PET tracers designed to visualize system x_c^- activity *in vivo* may eventually enable non-invasive measurement of SLC7A11 function in human subjects.

Tools for SLC7A11 Inhibition

Significant efforts have been directed toward the discovery of chemical tools to decrease the activity of SLC7A11 either by direct inhibition or decreasing protein expression. While the modalities do include oligonucleotide and antibodies, the majority of the effort thus far has been focused on small molecule modulators (**Figure 11**).

Erastin and related analogs, known for inducing ferroptosis, are the most attractive series reported to date^{27, 31, 53}. Many members of this class have shown sub-micromolar inhibition of both glutamate release and cystine uptake in LPS-treated rat primary microglial cells. Despite efforts to improve drug likeness, these compounds still suffer from poor solubility as well as high molecular weights and clogP values, and thus efforts must be made to improve this series for CNS targets⁵³. However, Erastin has been reported to affect other cellular targets, thus complicating its specificity and clinical application⁵⁴.

Figure 11. Representative small-molecule inhibitors of xCT (SLC7A11) activity, including the well-characterized Erastin series and the probable covalent inhibitor HG106. Several compounds, including Riluzole, Laniperisone, and Sorafenib, likely modulate SLC7A11 activity indirectly. Sulfasalazine and Hunan-1 are flagged as potential false positives due to structural features associated with PAINS (highlighted in red).

Sulfasalazine was first reported in 1948 for the treatment of rheumatic polyarthritis⁵⁵. Sulfasalazine and related analogs have since been reported to inhibit SLC7A11 with potencies in the micromolar range^{56, 57}. Thus, it requires high doses to achieve therapeutic effects in cancer treatment, leading to adverse off-target effects⁵¹. However, the diaryl-azo functional group has been identified as a common moiety of pan

assay interference (PAINS) compounds⁵⁸. This may be an underlying reason it has been reported to be active against multiple targets including NF- κ B⁵⁹, leukotriene C (LTC) synthetase and rat liver glutathione S-transferases⁶⁰, as well as possessing immunosuppressive, antifolate, lymphocyte inhibitory, and leucocyte modulatory actions⁶¹.

HG106 was identified by a screen of a commercial library measuring impact on glutathione production in A549 cells⁵¹. On-target specificity was performed by metabolic profiling and elimination of effect on SLC7A11 knock-down cells treated with siRNA. Treatment with HG106 led to decreased cystine uptake, reduced ROS production, and selective KRAS-mutant cancer cell toxicity. The chloroacetyl functional group suggests the possibility that this compound may be a covalent modifier of SLC7A11.

Riluzole is an anticonvulsant⁶² which has also shown anti-cancer⁶³ and neuroprotective^{64, 65} properties. While it is unlikely that Riluzole directly targets SLC7A11 itself, it has been shown to inhibit indirectly by reducing xCT protein levels in a 3-week xenograft study using human melanoma cell lines, C8161 and 1205Lu⁶⁶. The use of this molecule was taken even further by coupling with platinum in a prodrug manner for potential oncology treatments⁶⁷. However, Riluzole impacts many other transmembrane functions including Na⁺ channels⁶⁸, Ca²⁺-activated K⁺ channels⁶⁹, two-pore domain potassium channels TREK-1 and TRAAK⁷⁰, and hERG1 ion channels⁷¹.

Sorafenib (Nexavar) is a multikinase inhibitor approved for the treatment of various types of cancer⁷²⁻⁷⁴. Similar to Riluzole, Sorafenib exerts its influence on SLC7A11 indirectly by decreasing the transcription of SLC7A11, promoting the interaction of the natural inhibitor BECN1 with SLC7A11, and suppressing the cystine-glutamate exchange by lowering intracellular glutamate levels⁷⁵. Importantly for potential applications in treating neurodegenerative diseases, it has shown evidence of effectively crossing the blood brain barrier⁷⁶. Several analogs have been reported to impact ferroptosis with similar potencies⁷⁷. Unfortunately, Sorafenib severely damaged neurons in primary hippocampal cultures (containing neurons and glial cells) at clinically relevant concentrations⁷⁸ raising concerns for its long-term use.

Recently a new molecular starting point was discovered using a virtual screening approach⁴⁰. This molecule, that we refer to here as Hunan-1, was found to increase intracellular glutamate levels and decrease GSH levels at 25 μ M, but to a lesser extent compared to Erastin. While this compound is not technically flagged by PAINS filters, structural features such as the acylhydrazine and the possibility for tridentate chelation should be considered cautiously. Additionally, the structure received 156 demerits by the Lilly MedChem rules⁷⁹, surpassing the typical 100 demerit threshold and just narrowly missing the 160 demerit relaxed threshold. Taken together, we recommend further validation before this compound can be confidently used as an SLC7A11 inhibitor.

Many reports have been published⁸⁰⁻⁸² naming Lanperisone (LP) as an inhibitor of SLC7A11 or xCT each referencing Shaw et al⁸³. However, a careful reading of that report shows that the authors clearly state that the target of LP is unknown, though it may be connected to voltage gated sodium and calcium channels. It is also noted that the pharmacology has many similarities with Erastin which may be the source of the proposed LP-SLC7A11 connection. Until the molecular target of LP is definitively shown, one should take caution in the assumption that LP is a SLC7A11 inhibitor.

Several other compounds have been shown to decrease the expression and protein production of SLC7A11 including the PI3K inhibitor LY294002, Akt inhibitor Afuresertib, Raf inhibitor Dabrafenib, Ras inhibitor RBC8, and MEK1/2 inhibitor Selumetinib (AZD6244) having the greatest impact⁵¹.

The monoclonal antibody M5 has been reported to significantly reduce the uptake of FITC-cystine presumably due to its specific and high-affinity binding to the xCT complex. Furthermore, this mAb and associated antibody drug conjugate (ADC) were shown to reduce primary tumor formation and the number of lung metastases^{84,85}. Rolih and co-workers went further and even developed a virus-like particle (VLP)-based vaccine known as AX09 to elicit an antibody response against xCT⁸⁶.

As discussed above, reducing the expression of SLC7A11 can be a very effective strategy in lowering the glutamate activity in cells. Several groups have reported success using siRNA to knockdown SLC7A11 expression. Treatment with siRNA resulted in a decrease in intracellular cysteine and glutathione (GSH) levels along with the accompanying increase in ROS^{87,88}. Interestingly, the GSH levels could be rescued by treatment with *N*-acetyl-cysteine providing an SLC7A11-independent source of cysteine⁸⁷. Furthermore, SLC7A11 KD resulted in the decreased growth and even selective death of several cancer cell lines^{51, 66, 88}.

Discussion and Conclusion

System xc⁻ plays a critical dual role in CNS health by mediating cystine uptake for antioxidant defense and regulating extracellular glutamate levels through exchange transport. Healthy transport of glutamate is crucial for glutamate-glutamine cycling in neurons and astrocytes. However, too much glutamate leads to excitotoxicity and eventually neuronal loss. Thus, inhibition of SLC7A11 to limit extracellular glutamate seems appealing, but chronic SLC7A11 inhibition may impair astrocytic function, leading to secondary excitotoxic effects⁴⁵. System xc⁻ is the primary transporter responsible for the uptake of cystine, a major factor in GSH production. The depletion of GSH stores increases vulnerability to ferroptotic cell death, which can be exploited for the treatment of cancers, but is highly detrimental when applied to otherwise healthy neurons. One potential strategy to circumvent this pitfall is co-administration of *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC)⁸⁹. NAC is cell-permeable, needing no active transport assistance to enter the cell. Once inside the cell, it is rapidly converted to cysteine and available for GSH production⁹⁰.

Several agents across multiple modalities have successfully inhibited SLC7A11 activity as evidenced by decreased extracellular glutamate. As a membrane-localized transporter, SLC7A11 presents an attractive target for monoclonal antibodies, though BBB penetration remains a challenge. Similarly, siRNA-mediated knockdown offers a selective and effective means of inhibition. Recent advances in CNS delivery systems have made this a more feasible approach in clinical settings⁹¹⁻⁹⁴.

Among reported small-molecule inhibitors, the Erastin series remains the most thoroughly studied and promising scaffold. However, limitations in molecular weight, solubility, and metabolic stability will need to be addressed before clinical translation is feasible. The molecular weights are typically too large, as are the intrinsic clearance rates, and solubility remains a challenge. Modern property prediction software packages such as Simulations Plus ADMET Predictor[®] can be a valuable tool in designing novel structures with suitable physical properties for CNS drugs. Our understanding of the SLC7A11 binding pocket, including the key ligand-protein interactions required for potency, continues to grow. By integrating these structural insights with modern *in silico* predictive software, future inhibitors can be rationally designed to achieve both sufficient potency and optimized physicochemical properties for CNS drug development.

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